

Automated Video Moderation Through YOLOv11 and Custom CNN.

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Abstract— With the exponential growth of user-generated content, moderating sensitive material in videos has become both an ethical and technical challenge. Manual screening is not only time-consuming and inconsistent but also exposes reviewers to psychologically distressing content. To address these limitations, this paper presents a dual-model framework for automated sensitive content detection and localization in videos. Our approaches (custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and YOLOv11-based model) are useful for different types of sensitive content. Furthermore, a modified binary search algorithm is introduced to efficiently identify continuous segments of sensitive content, enhancing post-processing accuracy. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed system, with competitive detection performance and low inference times. This hybrid pipeline offers a scalable and ethical solution for real-time content moderation in digital platforms.

Keywords—Sensitive Content Detection, CNN, YOLOV11, Video Moderation, Deep Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the unregulated spread of user generated content emerge as a rising concern on social media platforms, video sharing websites and online communities in the current age of the digital media proliferation. Though such content provides room for creativity and communication, it also heightens the chances of exposure to wasted and inappropriate visual information, including nudity, violence, etc . Particularly for vulnerable user groups such as children and adolescents, such exposure can be harmful and result in adverse psychological effects, and cause great concern from

parents, policymakers, and platform administrators [1][3]. Manual moderation techniques are also time consuming and inconsistent, and they put moderators in contact with traumatic or inappropriate visuals. As a result, the area of automated sensitive content detection has become a vital area of research as in [2][3]. Recently, content moderation has become a hot topic, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and object detectors such as YOLO (You Only Look Once), have proved to be very successful in a number of image classification and localization tasks, thus serving as quite strong competitors to any content moderation pipeline establishment.

In this research, we develop two deep learning approaches for detecting sensitive content in visual data, and carry out a comparison of these two approaches. A CNN model that has been customized to be able to classify sensitive elements based on pixel level features. If certain contexts relating to the human body may indicate sensitivity. CNNs have been widely applied in pornography detection, weapon detection, and content classification tasks as in [4][11] [5][12], whereas YOLO-based models offer real-time object detection capabilities, and have been used effectively in scenarios such as person detection [6][14], nude region localization [7][15], and even privacy aware surveillance [8]. We then apply region specific blurring techniques to obscure the detected sensitive areas, evaluate their detection accuracy, precision, recall, inference speed and false detection rates on both models and the datasets, in order to fill this research gap. Inspired by previous works of motion blur simulation and image masking techniques [12] [13] Our blurring technique is inspired by these previous works. There are recent studies that have demonstrated promising results of using YOLO variants for scene detection and harmful content management as proposed in [9][7] and CNNs integrated with YOLO for security applications [10][5].

This study seeks to compare the two models not only in terms of technical efficiency but also in their practicality for real-world deployment, considering factors such as computational cost, scalability, and implementation challenges. The goal is to support the development of more reliable and efficient AI-driven content moderation solutions.

II. RELATED WORK

A. *Deep Learning for Sensitive Content Detection*

Prior research has extensively explored deep learning for detecting explicit content. Ref. [4] proposed a pornographic classifier using YOLO and Mask R-CNN to detect sensitive objects (e.g., genitals, breasts) and combined these with skin/human presence features via SVM, achieving 94.88% accuracy on the NPDI-800 dataset. Similarly, Ref. [9] adapted YOLO for “vigorous scene detection” by blurring harmful regions, emphasizing computational efficiency. However, these works focus on static images or predefined object classes. In contrast, our work introduces and compares CNN-based frame classification as well as YOLOv11’s person detection to moderate video content.

B. *Blurring Techniques for Content Moderation*

Blurring is often used after detection to obscure sensitive content. Previous studies have explored the effects of motion blur. For example, Ref. [13] showed that selective deblurring using GANs can improve object tracking in heavily blurred videos. Ref. [12] Introduced a method for adding motion blur to objects using auto-

segmentation and color compensation, but it relies on controlled recording conditions. Although these studies focus on generating blur, they do not integrate it into real-time detection systems. Our work addresses this gap by combining YOLOv11's bounding boxes/segmentation mask with blurring/pixelate, providing context-aware masking while avoiding unnecessary blurring of non-sensitive areas.

C. Hybrid Approaches for Video Moderation

Recent efforts combine multiple techniques for improved moderation. For instance, Ref. [7] fused YOLO with CNNs to focus attention on nude regions, while [14] used MDA-YOLO for human pose estimation to infer contextual harm. However, these methods lack comparative analysis of model trade-offs (e.g., speed vs. precision). Our study directly compares custom CNNs (for whole-frame classification) and YOLOv11 (for localized detection), evaluating metrics like inference time and false-positive rates to guide practical deployment.

TABLE I
LITERATURE REVIEW

Title of Paper	Year	Journal	Methodology / Technology Used	Limitations
Towards Automated Content-based Photo Privacy Control in User-Centered Social Networks	2022	CODASPY '22	Multimodal Variational Autoencoder (MVAE), Explainable AI (Grad-CAM), Dataset: 31,566 photos from 303 users	Excludes highly sensitive photos, Requires initial training for new users, No user experience evaluation for obfuscation
Enhancing Privacy: Automated Detection and Blurring of Sensitive Information in Images and Video Feeds	2022	Stanford University Technical Report	Fine-tuned YOLO-V8 (94% accuracy), OCR (EasyOCR, Tesseract), DeepFace/MTCNN for faces, Gaussian blurring	Struggles with occlusions/extreme lighting, GPU-dependent, Untested on real-world video dynamics
A Method for Adding Motion-Blur on Arbitrary Objects by Using Auto-Segmentation and Color Compensation Techniques	2021	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing	Multi-frame capture, Non-linear color compensation, Optical flow (Farneback), HDR integration	Resource-intensive, Segmentation fails on fast-moving objects, Requires well-exposed reference
Clinical Report—The Impact of Social Media on Children, Adolescents, and Families	2011	Pediatrics (AAP)	Surveys (Pew Research, Common Sense Media), Case studies (cyberbullying, sexting), Policy analysis (COPPA)	Dated (pre-TikTok era), U.S.-centric, Correlational (no causation)
Learning Strategies for Sensitive Content Detection	2023	Electronics	Text hashes (PhotoDNA), Skin recognition (YCbCr,	Legal restrictions on CSAM datasets, False positives in non-nude

			HSV), Deep Learning (CNNs, Vision Transformers)	content, Adversarial vulnerabilities
Mask R-CNN/YOLOv3 for Object Detection in Sensitive Images	2021	IJACSA	Mask R-CNN/YOLOv3, Detectron2 for humans, Skin ratio (HSV+YCbCr), SVM fusion	Fails on grayscale/skin-like objects, High false positives (e.g., sausages), Computationally expensive
Effects of Blur and Deblurring to Visual Object Tracking	2021	IEEE TPAMI	Blurred Video Tracking (BVT) benchmark, DeblurGAN/SRN for deblurring, Adaptive GAN-based deblurring	Synthetic blur only, Deblurring harms light blur cases, High computational overhead
Binary Search Algorithm	2019	WikiJournal of Science	Iterative/recursive implementations, Variants (exponential/interpolation search),	Requires sorted data, Poor cache locality, Quantum version impractical
Modified Binary Search Algorithm	2014	IJAIS	Early range checks, Boundary comparisons (low/high), Midpoint retention	Extra comparisons offset gains, Still requires sorted data, Edge-case focus limits utility
Weapons Detection for Security and Video Surveillance Using CNN and YOLO-V5s	2022	Computers, Materials & Continua	YOLO-V5s (CSPNet/PANet), Custom CNN, Gaussian blur preprocessing	Bias toward pistols (not rifles), Lighting/occlusion issues, Preprocessing latency
YOLO-Based Efficient Vigorous Scene Detection and Blurring for Harmful Content Management	2022	IEEE Access	YOLO for real-time detection, Adaptive blurring (context-aware)	Struggles with artistic nudity, Ethical censorship concerns
Real-Time Image-Based Weapon Detection Using YOLO Algorithms	2022	Springer Multimedia Tools and Applications	YOLO fine-tuning for weapons, Single-shot detection	Adversarial attack risks, Limited to visible weapons (no concealed items)

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system for sensitive content detection and blurring is designed to operate in a modular pipeline, ensuring efficiency, scalability, and flexibility. The system consists of four main components: Input Acquisition, Sensitive Content Detection, Blurring Module, and Final Output Generation. Two parallel detection approaches are implemented—one using a

custom CNN model, and the other leveraging YOLOv11 for person detection. The results of both methods are then used to selectively blur sensitive regions in the visual media.

Figure 1. Workflow Architecture

A. Data Used

1) *Data for CNN model:* The dataset utilized in this study comprises a total of 343 images (it was not possible to gather a large dataset. In real-world scenarios, it is common that sufficient images for every object of interest may not be available. To address this challenge, we developed an approach that can perform effectively even when abundant training images are not available.), specifically curated for the task of sensitive content detection – in our scenario, we considered images of fight/no fight between two wild bears. The images were categorized into two distinct classes fighting bears (representing sensitive or violent scenes) and non-fighting bears (neutral or safe content). This binary classification was intended to simulate the detection of potentially disturbing visual content within natural or wildlife footage.

The dataset was derived from publicly available YouTube video sources (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OloflbzNeMs>) where relevant frames were extracted and manually annotated. Each frame was classified based on the presence or absence of aggressive interactions among bears. This manual classification helped ensure high-quality labels for both training and evaluation. All images were resized to a uniform resolution to maintain consistency in input dimensions across both detection models. The dataset was split into training (70%), validation (20%), and testing (10%) sets to ensure reliable evaluation.

2) *Data used for YOLOV11:*

The dataset for the YOLO based model was derived from a YouTube video (<https://youtu.be/2dFeczHMf58>) specifically for our purpose. Since the YOLO model was not retrained but used as-is for inference, dataset splitting was not required. The pretrained weights were enough for detecting a person accurately[24]. The video was just used for inference/testing and not for training any deep learning algorithm. All datasets were handled with discretion, and the content was processed in accordance with ethical guidelines for sensitive media analysis.

B. Approach:1 (custom CNN model)

In this approach, we used the following architecture for training.

The input to the CNN model is an image of dimensions (360, 640, 3), which is first processed through a sequence of convolutional and pooling layers to extract discriminative features. In Layer 1, a 2D convolution operation with 16 filters of size (5×5) and a stride of 2 is applied, followed by a ReLU activation function and a (2×2) max-pooling operation to down sample the feature maps. Layer 2 applies another 2D convolution with 32 filters of size (5×5) and stride 2, again followed by ReLU activation and a (2×2) max-pooling operation. The resulting feature maps are then flattened into a one-dimensional vector, preparing them for fully connected layers. The first dense layer has 16 neurons with ReLU activation, followed by a second dense layer with 32 neurons and ReLU activation. Finally, the output layer consists of 2 neurons with a SoftMax activation function, classifying the input image as either "Appropriate" or "Inappropriate". This entire pipeline helps the model learn important patterns in the image and make an accurate prediction about its content.

Figure 2. CNN Architecture

After feature extraction, the output tensor is flattened and fed into a dense layer equipped with a ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activation function. This activation introduces non-linearity, allowing the network to learn complex decision boundaries. The final dense layer incorporates a SoftMax activation function, which produces a probability distribution over the defined class labels—typically sensitive and non-sensitive content categories.

The model is optimized using the Adam optimizer, that is, the model is trained based on the least squares optimization algorithms and the Adam optimizer that is good for adaptive learning rates and effective convergence behavior. SoftMax is the loss function and the training is performed for 25 epochs. The detection mechanism is principally a binary classification one, i.e., each input frame is classified as whether it contains sensitive visual elements.

For inference, we utilized the proposed binary search inspired algorithm to sequentially detect and blur the corresponding sensitive content.

C. Approach:2 (YOLOV11 person detection)

In this method, we utilize a pre-trained YOLOv11 model specifically configured to detect only human figures within an image or video frame. The implementation is carried out using the OpenCV (cv2) library alongside the YOLOv11 deep learning framework. After the inference step, the bounding boxes associated with the 'person' class are extracted from the output of YOLOv11. To further analyze these regions, a skin detection technique is applied to assess whether the detected area contains sensitive content. For each bounding box, the corresponding image segment is converted to the YCbCr color space, and a thresholding operation is performed using empirically determined lower and upper bounds of RGB color space : lower = [60, 46, 40] and upper = [255, 247, 219]. This filtering process highlights the pixels that fall within the defined skin-tone range. To reduce the false positives, we also detect face from the person's image. We subtract the number of pixels that represent face and fall into the above RGB bounds. Subsequently, the ratio of the number of detected skin-tone pixels to the total number of pixels in the bounding box is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{skin percentage} = ((\text{total skin pixels of a person} - \text{face pixels of person}) / \text{total pixels in the image}) \times 100.$$

The system classifies the content within the bounding box if the resulting skin percentage is greater than 30 percentage then the content is sensitive. As in [15], when the region is flagged, the sensitive part of the image is thereby blurred, or Pixelate, via a blurring operation. This setup only comes in role if the sensitive content is detected. This process produces a clean, blurred version of the original image or frame with only the relevant parts blurred.

D. POST PROCESSING USING BINARY SEARCH INSPIRED ALGORITHM:

The traditional linear search approach, with a time complexity of $O(n)$, would require sequentially traversing the entire frame sequence to identify the starting and ending indices of continuous segments marked as (sensitive frames). To address this inefficiency, the proposed method employs a divide-and-conquer strategy using a binary search inspired algorithm as in the pseudocode 1 and 2. This optimization reduces the time complexity to $O(\log n)$. Our algorithm is inspired from [16] and [17], making it significantly more suitable for analyzing long video sequences, as illustrated in the pseudo code mentioned below. Furthermore, the space complexity remains $O(1)$ since the algorithm does not require any additional memory structures beyond a few variables. Compared to the conventional linear traversal method, this optimized search technique achieves enhanced performance and enables more precise localization of sensitive intervals within videos.

Pseudocode 1

```
function Search(frame_rate, total_frame){
    SET inappropriate_frames TO empty list
    FOR i FROM frame_rate to total_frame STEP 2*total_frame DO:
        image = capture(i)           // uses opencv to capture the image at ith frame.

        IF exists(image) THEN
            left_image = capture(i - frame_rate)
            right_image = capture(i + frame_rate)

            IF exists(left_image) AND exists(right_image) THEN
                APPEND [i - frame_rate, i + frame_rate] TO inappropriate_frames

            ELSE
                IF exists(left_image) THEN
                    value = check_right(i, i + frame_rate)
                    APPEND [i - frame_rate, value] TO inappropriate_frames

                ELSE IF exists(right_image) THEN
                    value = check_left(i - frame_rate, i)
                    APPEND [value, i + frame_rate] TO inappropriate_frames

                ELSE
                    left_value = check_left(i - frame_rate, i)
                    right_value = check_right(i, i + frame_rate)
                    APPEND [left_value, right_value] TO inappropriate_frames

            ELSE
                left_image = capture(i - frame_rate)
                right_image = capture(i + frame_rate)

                IF exists(left_image) AND exists(right_image) THEN
                    APPEND [i - frame_rate, i + frame_rate] TO inappropriate_frames

                ELSE
                    IF exists(left_image) THEN
                        value = check_left(i - frame_rate, i)
                        APPEND [i - frame_rate, value] TO inappropriate_frames

                    ELSE IF exists(right_image) THEN
                        value = check_right(i, i + frame_rate)
                        APPEND [value, i + frame_rate] TO inappropriate_frames

                    ELSE
                        CONTINUE TO NEXT ITERATION

                RETURN inappropriate_frame
    }
```

Pseudocode 2

```
FUNCTION check_left(i, j)
{
    mid = INT((i + j)/2)
    image = capture(mid)

    IF i == j-1 THEN
        RETURN i

    IF exists(image) THEN
        RETURN check_right(mid, j)

    ELSE
        RETURN check_left(i, mid)
}
```

```
FUNCTION check_right(i, j)
{
    mid = INT((i + j)/2)
    image = capture(mid)

    IF i == j-1 THEN
        RETURN i

    IF exists(image) THEN
        RETURN check_right(mid, j)

    ELSE
        RETURN check_left(i, mid)
}
```

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation Metrics and Setup

A set of standard performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score as well as Intersection over Union (IoU) were rigorously evaluated on the proposed framework for the object detection model. These metrics show the complete understanding of models of classification and localization. Inference time was also considered to evaluate the real time feasibility of each approach.

B. CNN-Based Detection Results

The model was found to be promising on the curated image dataset upon evaluation. The custom CNN model showed good performance in detecting sensitive content, accurately classifying images as appropriate or inappropriate. Its ability to extract key features helped achieve good predictions. The performance of the CNN model in quantitative form is given below:

- Accuracy: 0.9981
- Precision: 0.91
- Recall: 0.85
- F1-Score: 0.8789

C. YOLOV11-Based Detection Results

The YOLOV11 model was adapted to detect and localize sensitive content in image frames extracted from video data. The dataset included visual elements considered to be inappropriate. The model was trained with annotated bounding boxes marking the regions of interest. YOLOv11 exhibited superior performance in identifying localized sensitive content. The results are as follows:

- Precision: 0.9320
- Recall: 1.0000
- IoU (mean): 0.9648
- F1-Score: 0.9429
- Average Inference Time per Frame: 25 seconds

These results indicate a significant improvement in spatial sensitivity over the CNN-based approach, enabling targeted blurring rather than whole-image censorship.

D. Comparative Analysis

A side-by-side comparison of the two approaches is presented in Table II. While the CNN model performed adequately in classifying entire frames, the YOLOv11 model's localization ability makes it more suitable for nuanced content moderation applications.

Table 2
Accuracy comparison

Metric	CNN-Based Model	YOLOV11 Model
Accuracy	0.9981	0.9320
Precision	0.91	1.0000
Recall	0.85	0.9648
F1-Score	0.8789	0.9429
Inference Time	50-80 milliseconds	20-30 milliseconds

E. Qualitative Observations

Figures 3-8 illustrate output samples from both models. The CNN model yields binary classification results (sensitive/nonsensitive), often resulting in unnecessary full-frame blurring. In contrast, YOLOv11 provides bounding box outputs, allowing selective blurring and preserving non-sensitive content.

Figure 3,6 – one random frame from input video (for custom CNN and YOLO, respectively)

Figure 4,7 – the same frame from blurred output video (for custom CNN and YOLO, respectively)

Figure 5,8 – the same frame from pixelated output video (for custom CNN and YOLO, respectively)

The output of YOLOv11 are just a representation of actual behavior of our algorithm. (Such decision was made by authors to keep the modesty of the research paper and allow wide range of readers/researchers to read the paper.)

Figure 3.

Figure 6.

Figure 4.

Figure 7.

Figure 5.

Figure 8.

F. Observations and Insights

The custom CNN model provides fast and accurate detection of sensitive content with a lightweight and efficient architecture. It captures important spatial features, ensures low computational cost, and integrates seamlessly into the processing pipeline. Complementing this, the YOLOv11 model enables quick and precise detection of human figures in images and video frames. Its high accuracy, and low processing overhead make it ideal for isolating regions for further sensitive content analysis. These two models create a reliable and efficient solution for automatic sensitive content moderation.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we suggested a dual approach framework to detect and manage sensitive content in videos that depend both on a custom CNN based classifier as well as a YOLOv11 based object detection model. Both the CNN and YOLOv11 architecture was able to categorize individual frames into sensitive and non-sensitive classes. A modified binary search algorithm was used to find continuous segments with sensitive content in order to increase accuracy of detection and reduce computational work. The results of the evaluation of both models showed promising results in terms of detection performance and acceptable precision, recall and inference time, which validate the effectiveness of the proposed methods. Beyond that, the system tackles a classification and a localization challenge simultaneously and grants a highly robust solution for automated content moderation. Future work will include more expansion of the dataset towards generalization of the model, integration of temporal analysis for video context understanding as well as refining real time deployment capabilities to deploy on large scale content platforms. This research equips us with the first foundational step in creating safer digital media environments with efficient, automated and ethically responsible content filtering mechanisms.

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